

Photo: Manuel Coser/CPR Torino

Briefing Paper on European pre-removal detention centers during the COVID-19 pandemic (March-May 2020)

**→ Specific view on the Czech Republic, Italy, Slovakia,
Spain, Sweden and the UK**

Human Rights and Migration Law Clinic 2020

“CPR-Research Group” composed by Simon Batik, Sara
Echevarria Castresana, Nebiat Lemenih Lenger, Jenny Nguyen & Enxhi Dule.

Supervised by Emanuela Roman, Ulrich Stege & Maurizio Veglio.

INTRODUCTION

This briefing paper draws on a report on the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on European pre-removal detention centres¹, drafted by students of the “CPR research group”, which is one of the teams of the legal clinic in Turin devoted to human rights and migrations (Human Rights Migration Law Clinic – HRMLC), a joint program in collaboration between the University of Turin, the Eastern Piedmont University and the International University College of Turin, together with the Italian association ASGI (Association for Legal studies on Migration).² All sources of information gathered can be found in the full report.

The purpose is to provide an overview of the situation for third-country nationals held during March until May 2020 in European pre-removal centres and developments that have occurred in this field in light of COVID-19. The focus has been on six country studies, namely the Czech Republic, Italy, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden and the United Kingdom. In this briefing paper, each country section highlights any relevant developments that have taken place since the outbreak of the pandemic, such as the release of detainees, the usage of alternative measures and the situation for those continuously confined in detention centres.

Though there is a quite wide terminology employed to depict measures of deprivation of liberty of undocumented migrants, this brief will focus on *pre-removal detention centers* (sometimes shortened as *detention centers* or *immigration detention centers*). In this brief, *pre-removal detention centers* refer to facilities where third-country nationals who have received an expulsion order are confined, while waiting for their expulsion orders to be implemented by the authorities. As such, facilities can differ depending on the national context, where it is relevant, any particular domestic terminology will be briefly highlighted.

¹ See news section of the IUC website: www.iuctorino.it.

² See: www.iuctorino.it or <https://www.clinichelegali.unito.it/do/home.pl>; the CPR Research group of the HRMLC is highlighting human rights problems related to immigration detention since 2012, see: <http://www.iuctorino.it/cie-research-project/>.

METHODOLOGY

In preparing the report that this briefing paper builds on, the research group employed a qualitative research methodology whereby primary and secondary data were collected and analyzed qualitatively. In some case studies, primary data was collected through questionnaires via email or telephone. The group consulted NGO representatives, campaigners, experts and government officials. The research group asked them general questions about immigration detention in their respective countries and what measures are being taken by governmental and non-governmental stakeholders to counter the spread of coronavirus in immigration detention centers.

The research group also asked them about whether the government is applying alternative to detention measures to release detainees, and what benefit packages are provided to those released. In collecting primary data, the researchers employed purposive sampling for flexibility reasons. National EU and international legislation regulating immigration detention was consulted. Media, newspapers, books, journals, reports, and bulletins were consulted as secondary data. Particularly, the researchers have explored the websites of NGOs, international organizations and government institutions. Reports by government authorities and campaigner groups were the major source of data. The group attempted to double check the reliability of information through the ad hoc consultation of national experts. However, the research group cannot guarantee the full certainty of the contents and its completeness.

The information included in the country case studies is updated to mid-May. All sources of information gathered can be found in the full report.

COUNTRY-SPECIFIC INFORMATION

→ CZECH REPUBLIC

BACKGROUND INFORMATION: *Czech Republic*

- Currently, 3 pre-removal centres are operating: Vyšní Lhoty, Balková and Bělá-Jezová
- The overall capacity of these centers is 916 beds, part of which is closed (currently there are only 488 places available).
- On 15.4.2020 there were 52 third-country Nationals detained in the whole country.
- Alternatives to detention are provided by the law but used rarely in practice.
- There is no debate about alternative measures such as release of detainees during COVID pandemic. Furthermore, the Refugee Facilities Administration of the Ministry of the Interior (hereinafter as RFA) stated that the *“detention centers are not like schools or other public institutions and can’t close.”*

The Czech Republic was among the countries that applied lockdown measures in very early stages of the coronavirus pandemic. However, the coronavirus pandemic had a little impact on the detention system in the country. The Refugee Facility Administration has stated that *“detention centers are not like schools or other public institutions and can’t close.”* The major change consisted in the establishment of a special detention section within the Bělá-Jezová detention center, where incoming migrants (who were still being accepted) are to be put under quarantine measures for at least 14 days. The obligatory entrance medical examination was already present before the measures taken in response to the coronavirus pandemic. For the third-country nationals already detained before the outbreak of the epidemic (numbering 52) the major change consisted in the limitation of legal counselling (provided virtually), distribution of face masks and hand sanitizers and restriction of interpersonal contacts. The restrictions are directed mainly towards the incoming personnel.

Czech Republic has been highly criticized for detention of families with children and also because detainees have to pay for their own detention. The conditions have improved since the refugee crisis of 2014-2016. Yet, the alternatives to detention are still rarely used and during the coronavirus crisis the release of detainees was not an option. During our research, there has not been any case of new detention.

→ ITALY

BACKGROUND INFORMATION: *Italy*

- **Nine pre-removal detention centers, CPR (Centro di permanenza per i rimpatri), and four Hotspots are operating in Italy.**
- **According to the last available statistics, the capacity of CPRs is of 525 detainees in total. As of 30th May 2020, some 178 third-countries Nationals were held inside centres, mostly in the pre-removal detention center of Torino. Some 218 people are detained in Hotspots.**
- **As of 22 May 2020, five undocumented migrants in the pre-removal detention center of Gradisca d'Isonzo were found positive to COVID-19.**
- **Even though the total number of detainees decreased during the COVID-19 pandemic, no official statement on suspension of deportation has been issued.**

Italy was in many respects the EU country which was most affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. On 8 March 2020 the Italian government expanded the quarantine to all the country. Everyone in Italy for a period of three months lived under a mandatory lockdown that restricted working practices and freedom of movement. As a consequence, all travels from or to Italy were cancelled. In a number of different ways, the lock-down effects of trying to contain COVID-19 also limited operations to assist migrants and asylum seekers, themselves at risk from the virus.

From the beginning of the health emergency, the National Ombudsman called on the responsible authorities to carefully consider the condition of migrants detained in pre-removal detention centres. Even though return procedures are extremely difficult, if not impossible, to fulfil and centres are arguably unsafe places for detainees, judicial authorities – namely Judges of the Peace (“Giudici di Pace”), nonprofessional judges responsible for pre-removal detention center – were still validating requests from Police to extend the detention of third-country nationals. On the contrary some decisions from Courts (“Tribunali”), where professional judges are in charge of detention of asylum seekers in pre-removal detention centers, denied the extension of detention. This demonstrated that there was not a unified practice across the country. Political positions over migration have hardened too.

Hundreds of associations like ASGI and individuals signed a public statement highlighting the critical conditions of third-country nationals detained in pre-removal detention center. According to signatories, detainees and personnel of the centres were highly exposed to the risk of infection, due to structural reasons and to the access of people from outside.

The number of undocumented migrants detained in the pre-removal detention centers has been gradually been reduced. According to the National Ombudsman, at the beginning of the crisis around 400 undocumented migrants were detained. As for 22 May 2020, some 195 were still detained.

In addition, the COVID crisis added another important problem to the Italian Hotspots. The decree no. 150 of 7 April 2020 establishes that, during the health emergency caused by the spread of Covid-19, Italian ports cannot be classified as safe places, place of safety, for the landing of migrants. On 12 April, Decree no. 1287/2020 of the Head of the Civil Protection Department was published, entrusting the Department for Civil Liberties and Immigration of the Ministry of the Interior with the management of procedures related to the fiduciary isolation and quarantine of foreign citizens rescued or arrived independently by sea. On the basis of this decree, the Ministry of Interior, together with the Italian Red Cross, may use ships for the “health surveillance” period “with reference to persons rescued at sea and for whom it is not possible to indicate the “Place of Safety”. This indication, apparently sibylline, refers to the persons referred to in the decree of 7 April, i.e. persons rescued outside the Italian SAR by ships flying a foreign flag for which Italian ports cannot

be considered “safe places”. Migrants arriving autonomously, i.e. not as a result of SAR operations, should in the first instance carry out the quarantine period in reception facilities on the territory and not on ships, unless it is for some reason impossible to identify such facilities, as in fact happened for many people disembarked in Italy in May and June.

Particular attention deserves the future of this praxis. The hotspots themselves were set up in 2015 as an extraordinary measure to deal with a situation where the number of people arriving in Italy and Greece was extremely high. However, this system, having ended “the emergency”, continued to operate and became fully integrated into the ordinary management system of migration, revolutionizing it and introducing serious violations of the rights of foreign citizens. It is therefore a serious risk that quarantine ships do become the forerunner of “hotspot ships”, “hotspot platforms” or other systems aimed at preventing foreign citizens rescued at sea from disembarking in Italy. The conditions of the ships, their structural isolation, the difficult monitoring and the impossibility of the contacts with civil society, make this formula absolutely inadequate for carrying out the delicate operations of reception, information, definition of the legal status of foreign citizens.

→ SLOVAKIA

BACKGROUND INFORMATION: *Slovakia*

- **Two pre-removal detention centers are currently operating: Medved'ov & Sečovce.**
- **The overall capacity is 328 persons.**
- **By end of April 2020, in Medved'ov there were no detained third-country Nationals while in Sečovce there are 50 detained third-country Nationals.¹**
- **Alternatives to detention are provided by law but rarely used due to strict eligibility criteria and insufficient examination of the possibility of their application by police in practice when deciding on detention.**
- **There was no debate about alternative measures such as release of detainees during COVID pandemic.**
- **Deportations have been stopped for the duration of the crisis.**

Slovakia is regularly one of the countries with the lowest numbers of asylum applications in Europe and during our research (April 2020), one of the detention centers was empty (Medved'ov) while in the other one (Sečovce) there were 50 detainees.

Non-governmental organization Centrum Právnej Pomoci has stated that *“the situation shouldn't have a huge effect on already detained migrants.”* However, some detainees have expressed concerns due to insufficient medical care and lack of protective materials (hand sanitizers and face masks).

The main attention was given to newcomers and according to the Human Rights League, newly detained foreigners are placed in a separated section under quarantine for at least 14 days. Migrants who were already in detention were not released and there is no debate about alternative measures, which are rarely used in practice (although provided by the law). Deportations were stopped. In this respect, non-governmental organizations dealing with legal issues (e.g. Human Rights League) raised their voice and stated that the continuation of detention without possibility

of expulsion is “*contrary to Article 17 of the Constitution of the Slovak Republic, the case law of the Constitutional Court of the Slovak Republic, as well as Article 5 (1) (f) of the European Convention on Human Rights and the relevant case law of the European Court of Human Rights.*”

→ SPAIN

BACKGROUND INFORMATION: *Spain*

- There are 8 working pre-removal detention centers: Barcelona, Madrid, Valencia, Algeciras, Gran Canaria, Tarifa, Murcia and Tenerife. There are also two temporary stay centers for migrants (CETIs) in the cities of Ceuta and Melilla.
- The overall capacity of the pre-removal detention centers is around 1.200 - 1.500. The capacity of the CETIs is of 512 (in Ceuta) and 480 detainees (in Melilla).
- Alternatives to detention are provided by law but rarely used.
- During the end of March and the beginning of April, due to the Covid-19 pandemic and the impossibility to deport third-country Nationals, the 8 pre-removal centers were progressively emptied.

Since the Spanish government declared the state of emergency on the 14th of March, the situation of the pre-removal detention centers was uncertain. The first response came from the supervisory judges of each center to implement sanitary measures, which was in itself a challenge considering the lack of space in the facilities. In the following days, third-country nationals started to be gradually released from the centers in Valencia and Barcelona.

On the 19th of March, the Spanish Ombudsman asked the government to release all the detainees on the grounds that their deportation was not going to be carried out due to the lockdown. Following these declarations, there were more protests coming from the detainees along with strong public campaigning. Also, other pre-removal centers started to release more detainees. All the 8 pre-removal detention centers were empty by April the 10th, except for 4 detainees still remaining in Algeciras until the 10th of May. The release of third-country nationals was conducted

generally on a case-by-case basis and on the grounds of the incapability to deport or because they reached the maximum time of detention (60 days), but the judges also took into account their safety.

The Minister of Interior stated that there were not going to be any deportations taking place, due to the closed borders. Also, there were no new detentions. The released third-country nationals that did not have a place to stay, after being released were welcomed by a humanitarian program coordinated by the Ministry of Inclusions, Social Security and Migration and NGOs.

In the cities of Ceuta and Melilla, there are two Centers of Temporary Stay for Immigrants (CETIs), in which asylum seekers, families and undocumented migrants are kept while their deportation is organized. During the outbreak of Covid-19, these centers continued working, in contrast with the closure of centres in the Spanish mainland and islands. The centre in Melilla tripled its capacity and some positive cases of Covid-19 were reported.

→ SWEDEN

BACKGROUND INFORMATION: *Sweden*

- There are in total 6 pre-removal detention centers in Sweden. These are located in Flen, Gävle, Märsta, Åstorp, Kålleröd and Ljungbyhed, and are referred to as förvarin the Swedish legislation.
- According to the last available statistics from the Swedish Migration Agency (May 2019), the maximum capacity in total is around 500. There is no available and up-to-date official statistics on how many persons are currently held in the pre-removal detention centers.
- Starting from mid-March 2020, there were reports on unrests amongst detainees due to the COVID-19. Simultaneously, the authorities have started releasing detainees on an individual assessment basis, based on the lack of prospect of carrying out expulsions in the foreseeable future.
- Supervision is an alternative to detention that is provided for in Swedish legislation. The measure entails that the individual in question needs to report to authorities with regular intervals. The measure is applied to a certain extent, and most notably so for those released from pre-removal detention centers due to COVID-19 affecting the prospect of expulsion decisions being carried out.
- There is no official call for suspension of expulsions and voluntary returns are carried out to the extent it is possible. Nonetheless, forced expulsions have decreased and are difficult to carry out due to various travel bans.

From mid-March, the reports on COVID-19 in Sweden started to highlight the situation in the pre-removal detention centers. The first COVID-19 case was confirmed on the 18th of March in the pre-removal center of Märsta, central Sweden. A few days prior to this, one of the largest Swedish NGO networks, *Flyktinggrupperna Riksråd (FARR)*, demanded a ban on deportations and the release of detainees in light of COVID-19. Simultaneously, there was unrest in pre-removal detention centers

and some initiated a hunger strike to protest against facilities not closing down despite the health risks as well as the impossibility to carry out expulsions.

There has been internal communication within the Swedish detention centers on how to handle possible COVID-19 cases, resulting in the creation of additional or the extended use of isolation spaces as quarantine. Nonetheless, staff and people held in detention centers have criticized the lack of protective gear and the limited possibilities to practice social distancing due to the spatial boundaries, shared bedrooms, dining areas and hygienic facilities.

During the beginning of April, hundreds of detainees were released from detention centers, followed by reports on an informal ban on deportations due to travel restrictions, less available flights and closed borders. Those released have been put under supervision, which is an alternative measure to detention that requires an individual to present themselves to the authorities, often once or twice a week. No official ban on expulsions has been declared from the authorities. There is a lack of specific numbers of the updated situation in the detention centers, which has to do with the general lack of official and updated statistics in this field.

Nonetheless, the pre-removal detention centers in Sweden have not officially closed down and have continued to function e.g. with new entries during the same period that measures were taken due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Furthermore, there have been indications of the risk of arbitrary decisions, lack of transparency from the authorities as well as inadequate measures taken to ensure the health of the detainees.

→ UNITED KINGDOM

BACKGROUND INFORMATION: UK

- There are seven Immigration Removal Centers (IRC) and two residential short-term holding facilities in the UK. There is no time limit on immigration detention.
- As of May, 2020, 368 people are detained in UK immigration Removal Centers.
- The U.K. has released more than 700 immigration detainees amidst coronavirus.
- Detention and removals continued during COVID-19.
- Two COVID-19 cases have been reported in IRCs (one in Brook House and one in Yarl's Wood). There is, however, no published policy on testing within immigration removal centres.
- UK immigration law recognized alternative to detention measures. During the pandemic, the home office granted bail for detainees.
- In UK immigration detention was down to its lowest level in at least 10 years.

On March 22 a woman tested positive for the coronavirus at Yarl's Wood Immigration removal center. Another case was later reported in Brook House Immigration Removal Center. Before and after the outbreak of the virus in detention centers, different NGOs and charities questioned the legality of detention at this particular time. On March 19, Detention Action, a UK based charity, took legal action for the release of detainees and successfully challenged the Home Office. Following the legal action, the UK Home Office released 350 people held under immigration detention.

Removal and detention continued during the pandemic. In March, the Home Office halted the new detention of those liable to administrative removal to 49 countries. However, despite a confirmed case in Yarl's Wood Immigration Removal Center, women detainees continued to be sent to the center. Moreover, a man who had tested positive to COVID-19 in Brook House Immigration Removal Center was detained on 2 April 2020. During the lockdown, on the 30th of April, the UK Home Office arranged a charter flight to Poland and successfully removed undocumented migrants.

On May 13, it is reported that the number of detainees in the UK in immigration removal centers downed to 368. This number is recorded as the lowest in ten years. Including those 350 detainees released by the High Court`s order in March, so far more than 700 people have been released from immigration detention during the COVID-19 crisis. People released who had no friends or family to live with could apply for public accommodation upon release. Yet, NGOs argue that due to the government`s housing policies the probability of getting accommodation for these persons is too low; hence, they risk becoming homeless.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Pre-removal immigration detention is an administrative measure and not a criminal punishment, and it is supposed to be used only in order to facilitate expulsion. From a more general perspective, it is equally important to note the severe nature of deprivation of liberty, as reflected in various international human rights instruments calling for a prohibition of arbitrary deprivation of liberty. Against this background, it is important to further discuss the legality of continued detention in pre-removal centers in light of COVID-19.

Article 15(4) of the EU Return Directive, applicable in this context, stipulates that “[w]hen it appears that a reasonable prospect of removal no longer exists for legal or other considerations or the conditions laid down in paragraph 1 no longer exist, detention ceases to be justified and the person concerned shall be released immediately.”

The prerequisite of “reasonable prospect” is of importance. The travel restrictions implemented globally in response to the COVID-19 pandemic have severely restricted cross-border movement. Naturally, this has affected the possibility to carry out expulsion decisions, since the dramatic decrease of flights operating and countries not accepting forced returns. Hence, the prerequisite of “reasonable prospect of removal” cannot be regarded as fulfilled. Accordingly, the third-country Nationals held in pre-removal detention centers and whose expulsions are impossible to carry out – shall be released immediately.

However, apart from Spain, the detention centers studied in this report were still functioning. Reiterating that deprivation of liberty of migrants in general should be used restrictively due to it being such a harsh measure and underlining the prerequisite of “reasonable prospect of removal” for detention centers, the legality of continued detention of third-country nationals is therefore more than questionable.

There are two opposite lines of argument about how safe detention centers are during coronavirus. The first one is that, because of the crowded and shared environments and the potential risk of contagion brought by staff members and new intakes, immigration detainees are more vulnerable to the coronavirus disease. Because they are living in proximity, it is impossible to effectively practice social distancing measures in detention centers. Also, people in detention are believed to have a greater burden of disease and worse health conditions than the general population. They frequently face greater exposure to health risks such as smoking, poor hygiene and weak immune defense due to stress, poor nutrition or pre-existing diseases. All these factors make people living in detention centers more vulnerable to infections. Based on this, different stakeholders, including doctors, called for the release of detainees and succeeded to some extent.

To the contrary, other stakeholders argue that even if it is good to release detainees, it is necessary to provide them proper support including accommodation. However, if the government is not providing them accommodation, some detainees released will be homeless. Therefore, in this particular situation it is better to remain in detention centers for the safety of detainees and of the overall population. It is about choosing the lesser evil. The research group believes that detention centers are not a safe place to detainees during the pandemic, hence releasing them is necessary to limit the spread of the virus. As different reports by NGOs and charities claim that authorities are releasing detainees without proper preparation on the post-release life, it is our position that governments should strengthen their efforts to provide accommodation and other assistance upon and after release.

Taking into consideration the widespread criticism to immigration detention systems and the complicated situation caused by the Covid-19 crisis, the release of detainees seemed like a positive and even necessary step to take. In this regard, the actions taken by Spanish authorities stand out. Spain managed to empty all its detention centers and implemented alternatives to detention where

normally they are not widely used. This can be a positive example, which shows that detention should be a measure of last resort and that there is capacity to accommodate third-country Nationals who do not have a place to stay. Nonetheless, the process of releasing detainees was not linear, and it was pushed by public campaigning, detainees' protests and the petition of the Spanish Ombudsman. In some cases, as in the center of Gran Canaria, the release was the only way to stop the fast spread of Covid-19 among those in the center. Conversely, we should not forget that the situation in the centers of Ceuta and Melilla has not improved and there are serious overcrowding issues that challenge public safety.

On a different note, a general issue that has been stressed continuously in all the case studies was the lack of clear, accessible and official information. This issue has been expressed previously to the Covid-19 outbreak by social movements and NGOs in relation to the management of pre-removal centers. Moreover, when dealing with a health emergency such as the current pandemic, access to transparent information becomes vital. In most cases, information concerning the number of people in detention and the number of those released was not easily or officially accessible. Information on the implementation of alternatives to detention was equally hard to access. Not only is this information out of reach for the general public, but also to NGOs that are active on the issue of immigration detention. When the authorities took decisions such as releasing a group of detainees (or not) or putting an end to the NGOs' visits into the centers, the flow of information was not constant and there was no predictability. This critic falls directly onto the authorities for lacking transparency and not having the will to change this.

A limit on the duration of detention or, generally speaking, information about a person's presumed length of detention is a precondition without which not even a criminal prison would be allowed to operate. However, in the United Kingdom the limit on the duration of detention is not stated by the law. Despite huge criticism and several attempts (like a parliamentary inquiry calling for a 28-day time limit on detention in 2018) indefinite detention is still in place.

In response to the coronavirus pandemic, a similar pattern has occurred in Slovakia, the country with the lowest level of detention in our study. As a response to the coronavirus pandemic, the National Council of the Slovak Republic approved an amendment to the Act on the Residence of Aliens, according to which *"enforcement of an administrative expulsion decision is suspended for the*

duration of a crisis. This postponement shall not constitute grounds for release from reinsurance under Article 90 (2) (b) (1)." As we can see in this example, Slovak Republic in response to the coronavirus pandemic moved closer to the UK model of indefinite detention without releasing any detainees (which was instead the case for the UK).

Generally, this report, covering the United Kingdom, Spain, Italy, Sweden, Czech Republic, and Slovakia raised different legal and practical concerns related to immigration detention. Based on different sources of data the research group tried to highlight how immigration detention looks like in this particular period of crisis. Many of the concerns highlighted in the report are linked to the system of immigration detention in general. Thus, in light of all these concerns, Member States should carefully reflect about the use of immigration detention in general, but in particular in times of health crisis – such as the current COVID-19!